

1

This woman was feeling too tired to do anything. Everything was an effort.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

2

This woman felt really worried a lot.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

3

This woman felt so sad, nothing could make her feel happy.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

4 This woman felt like everything in her life was no good. She felt hopeless.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

5 This woman felt really jumpy. She had to move or walk about a lot.

In the last 4 weeks (2 pays) have you felt like this?

Notes

1	—
2	—
3	—
4	—
5	—
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Total _____	